

A Teacher's Autoethnography on The Effectiveness of Semester System on a Master's Degree

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Abstract

The semester system is thought to be better than the yearly system of education. However, various barriers to the effective running of the semester system have to be managed before we realize its fruitfulness. The starkest indicators of the effectiveness of any education system are academic achievement, prompt employability, and entrepreneurship. The academic calendar, curriculum, physical infrastructures of education, and skilled human capital (educators and administrators) are important pillars of success. More important are students who need to be willing to adapt to unconventional ways of learning that demand more hard work. The students themselves should be active while the college is a platform and professors show the direction. During the five years of my assistant professorship in the subject of psychology, I found that the semester system is no better than the annual system because students come with the same old mindset of sitting passively and listening up to teachers. They barely complete all the assignments or presentations. The teachers are unskilled for the new market demands and applied aspects. They need to be trained. Incentives are not enough. Salary, wages, and facilities should be availed competitively. The country should honor the teachers and a management system should be set up in a way they perform the best honestly. This autoethnography of mine presents the problems existing in the semester system with respect to psychology subject and suggestions I have realized that can be adopted to improve on it.

Keywords: *Tribhuvan University, annual system, Psychology, andragogy, curriculum.*

Prologue

I have taught some batches of semester students in MA of Psychology since I joined Tribhuvan University as an UpaPraadhyaapak in 2017. I will discuss from the perspective of this subject which is a behavioral/social science that is expected to be highly applied. If I have to talk as a part-time teacher, the semester system has overload and underpay. If I talk as a permanent faculty, I still will have complaints

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about the large number of students, more than a teacher can handle compromising the quality of teaching and learning experience.

Introduction

Master's degree in Psychology in Tribhuvan University (TU) is now in the semester system. Psychology, the study of affect, behavior, and cognition (Adhikari, 2020), is taken by students and teachers both as a cerebral luxury or a tool for the solution of individual/group problems or both. It has both basic and applied scopes. Higher education has a history of more than a century. TriChandra College was established in 1918 and the establishment of Tribhuvan University followed. The semester system was exercised in the past also. Recently in 2014, this system was reintroduced from central departments and other colleges followed suit.

I was selected as an *UpaPradhyaapak* and posted to TriChandra College (TRC) in July 2017. I was sent for the Bachelor's degree and was busy teaching for it. It was an associate professor Dr. Bharati Adhikari who recommended me for a Master's degree (run as a private program at TRC) and another associate professor Dr. Ram Chandra Aryal (the then coordinator) who gave me a chance to teach History and Systems of Psychology (Psy551) and Qualitative Research Methods (Psy558) to the first and second semesters respectively. I was also invited to the Central Department of Psychology (CDP) for Quantitative Research Methods (Psy553) as a part-time teacher. It was the thrill and excitement to teach at a Master's degree. My anxiety was very high on the first class at TriChandra with almost 75 students. There were students from various backgrounds. Some first classes were anxiety-arousing because of my lack of experience and my high regard/scare for a Master's degree. Following experiences with two colleges and a semester, I was invited for Applied Psychometrics (Psy559) for PadmaKanya College (PKC) as a part-timer in the following semester. It was surprising to me that within the same university across constituent colleges, a permanent faculty was being treated as a part-timer rather than a guest.

The beauty of the semester system lies in the nature of course management and the role of teachers/students. Semester means a duration of six months. So, the academic calendar should be made in a way that teaching/learning and evaluation is completed in six months. There are at least five subjects in each semester. The students are given assignments (some of them are field-based), they have to present the thing they have read and understood, and they have to complete mini-research. There are traditional examinations in the semester system of Tribhuvan University. A teacher is a guide who shows the path to relevant sources and references and manages class so that students, being active themselves, learn in an animated manner. They can provide 40% of marks to students in the semester system of Tribhuvan University (Central Department of Psychology [CDP], 2013). Tribhuvan University is set to catch up with

an international standard of educating (Higher Education Reform Project [HERP], 2019). So, it has reintroduced the semester system in Master's degrees and aims to expand it in all Bachelor's degrees.

There are various pluses of the semester system. The assignments in the semester system have enabled students to be autonomous learners (Kadel, 2021) but the teachers' skills to supervise need to be increased. The assignments are more about writing essays rather than life-related tasks. Students get to learn many subjects. They have the chance to learn by doing practical work. The academic calendar helps manage time for the students' degrees.

The pitfalls of the semester system are cost and rush. The other weaknesses are a lack of qualified workforce (both teaching and managing) and infrastructure to provide practical training as imagined by the curriculum. The teachers are under continuous pressure to evaluate the work of students. In other words, students and teachers must work harder.

Method

The autoethnographic method (in qualitative research design) has been adopted. Autoethnography is about telling "stories of/about the self told through the lens of culture" and "analytic demonstrations of how we come to know, name, and interpret personal and cultural experience" (Adams et al., 2015). It is concerned with using the researcher's experience to critique cultural and social practices. It gives voice to personal experiences to extend social knowledge (Wall, 2008). For example, Hayler (2011) sought to know how teachers form professional identity and practice based on narratives of experience. I have relied on memory and some digital/physical artifacts remaining in my computer/residence. I effortfully recalled the events and experiences to complete this article. The imagery of my ex-students and some events was useful to recall my past experiences.

Findings

I divide this section into two parts: current weaknesses and my suggestions for improvement. First, I describe weaknesses in curriculum, lack of materials, problems with time management, imposed content, teaching-learning gap, traditional mindset, domination of theory, and poor quality control under current weaknesses of the semester system. Finally, I will describe my suggestions to better the semester system including hybridizing teaching-learning, lowering teacher-student hierarchy, documentation, contextualizing curriculum, increasing educator-management coordination, and investing in human capital under suggestions.

Current Weaknesses

Flaws in Curriculum

Many weaknesses in the curriculum are a major barrier to the success of the semester system. The repetition of contents across various subjects, emphasis on redundant theories, syllabus without context (e.g., Psy551 is the first paper in the first semester that has history and systems of Psychology without introducing what it is), lack of content integration, and having practical works that are not suitable for current demands of the market (for example, pure lab works such as tachistoscope on Psy555/Cognitive Psychology) are some of the weaknesses in the curriculum (CDP, 2013). Occasional updates/revisions to the curriculum are necessary to make the semester system more potent. The changes in curriculum are inevitable. For example, the Population Studies Curriculum has adopted the policy orientation evolving from theoretical and technique-based one (B. Acharya, 2011). The syllabi place emphasis on joining subjects with everyday experience. Nevertheless, the teaching is being done in an opposite way (Nakawa, 2013). Research is needed to find out what factors cause such a nuance.

Professor Dr. Shanta Niraula gave me the first chance at CDP. I had asked how I should teach the MA students. She said, "You can get reflection of the quality of your teaching on students' faces." The first subject I started to teach was Psy553 (Quantitative Research Methods) at CDP. I found that the prescribed textbook had a sociological approach. So, it was not very suitable for a psychology course. The second subject I taught was History and Systems of Psychology (Psy551) at TRC. Psy551 has some philosophical terms irrelevantly and they overlap with some contents in Psy553. The third subject I taught was Qualitative Research Methods (Psy558) at TRC. Psy558 has atlas.ti as a computer application to teach but it is not open-source software. The college has not bought it either. Psy553 and Psy558 combined do not have ethical issues for psychological research. The fourth subject I taught for the MA degree was Applied Psychometrics (Psy559) at PKC. Psy559 has four approaches to test construction that are not found in detail in recommended books. Psy559 repeats many contents of Psy553. I taught Psy558 for three batches at PKC and four batches at TRC. I realized that the philosophical/theoretical contents occupied a large portion of Psy558. The fifth subject I taught was Human Factors Psychology (Psy562-2) at CDP. Professor Dr. Nandita Sharma invited me to teach this subject. Its syllabus was entirely based on a single book but some chapters were missed out from the book. In its current state, the content is difficult to cover in a semester's teaching timeframe. Still, the chapters should have been included to provide students the chance to provide a complete understanding of the subject to the students.

The success of the semester system depends upon institutional autonomy which has been dampened in Tribhuvan University because of political interference and unruly activities of teacher associations or employee unions, and low job control of heads of departments or program coordinators (P. R. Joshi, 2016). For months, the administration remains padlocked for some unreasonable demands of some eccentric associations/unions oftentimes. TRC administration is under the lock as this article is being written on 2022 May 15.

In 2018, a decision to not allow graduates of Clinical Psychology the chance to practice psychological counseling incited a rebellion of CDP students. They dragged TRC students to their movement. I remember that the classes at TRC were disturbed for some weeks that year. Students in the first semester had sought suggestions from me also if they should join the movement. Finally, the movement succeeded and the authority had to revert the decision.

Lack of materials

In the classroom, the materials are often lacking. Sometimes the projectors are not working and sometimes the laptops are not working. Sometimes markers are missing and at other times whiteboards are unwritable. Infrastructure development is a must (Baral et al., 2019) for the effectiveness of the semester system. An important aspect of an MA degree is the thesis. For a long, we suffered from the lack of access to research databases. Now, after the COVID-19 pandemic, TU Central Library (TUCL) has made off-campus access to some databases like ProQuest possible. This is a praiseworthy thing but the number of databases is not enough if we want to have world-class studies done from our students or faculties.

Materials to teach were lacking in many moments. Had there not been a website (maybe a pirate!) to download the book mentioned as a textbook in the syllabus, I would be helpless. Why do not colleges readily avail books mentioned in the library? This would be helpful to both students and teachers. I assert that the materials to study should be prepared before the release of the syllabus. In the morning classes at PKC, oftentimes, I have used markers bought with my own money to write. The case of other colleges is not that different. Coordinators are rarely found in colleges and other administrative staff (who are very few) are unavailable when needed. No college provides SPSS and atlas.ti mentioned in syllabi to teachers. The teachers are obligated to use cracked/pirated versions. This lack of human and material resources should be promptly addressed.

During the pandemic, teachers taught online with their own resources. Initially, I had an ADSL connection to the internet at my home in Kavre. Later, I had to change it with a broadband connection (based on optical fiber) from a private ISP at Rs.14300

from my private fund. I used my own laptop. We can do such things during difficult times out of kindness/empathy/accountability. University had issued directives to colleges to support teachers in infrastructures but they did not comply. The colleges do not offer proper seats/cabins/devices for performing our tasks like checking students' assignments or theses. How long will this paucity go? I feel that the university should send clear directives about seating arrangements and the availability of resources like computers and the internet for teachers and professors teaching in the semester system. I did not have my cabinet to store the assignment submitted by students on any of the three campuses I taught. This affected the quality of evaluation of assignments because I had to return the assignment instantly or my work-life balance because I had to take them home to interfere with my personal time.

Figure 1. Resources for research provided by TUCL. These can be accessed off-campus. This is a positive start but these resources are limited.

Time Management Issues

Master's degree courses are run in the evening or in the morning. The students arrive late and leave early because of jobs, cold, transportation problems, or night. It is difficult to complete the course. The students do not get enough time to prepare for the internal exam. The *viva voce* of practical works also consumes a lot of time. The teachers remain very busy but they are paid less. So, work-life balance has been

disturbed on several occasions. Because the results are published very late, there is a negative impact on students in the following examinations.

Imposed content

"A person makes a syllabus, the second person teaches, the third person makes exam questions, the fourth person checks the exam sheets, and no person should be accountable if the students' results are bad". This thought recurs in my mind often.

The curriculum has been imposed on teachers (Paudel, 2019). This ignores the essence of the semester system which should have teachers' participation in designing and implementing the curriculum. The senior professors imposing curriculum without the understanding of context comes from a hierarchical mindset. Many typos in the curriculum indicate the fact that syllabi are not designed with the required seriousness. A challenge is the centralized education system (Giri, 2021). University is planning to provide all rights to colleges (HERP, 2019) but currently, the centralized education system is a challenge (Giri, 2021).

Teaching-Learning Gap

Despite two subjects teaching specifically research methods and many research-based assignments, students seem to be very weak in their research skills as they get to the fourth semester for the thesis. They lack the fundamental skills related to research. Except for some exceptional students, many students procrastinate their thesis and leave it undone for years. A problem is with their bachelor's degree which does not prime them with an inquisitive mind and inquiring attitude. Another problem is the lack of motivation in students for assignments. A factor for this lack of motivation is the teachers' inability to inspire them to identify research problems of their interest or that which is very close around them. Another problem may be the lack of opportunity to get supervised individually. Teachers' lack of skills in subject matter, management, technology, and teaching techniques are also to blame. They should be trained in all these domains.

A student of mine who I had tutored in the first and second semesters recently completed his thesis last April. Then, I thought he was a good student. However, as a protégé, he could not prove his worth. The student was willing to complete the thesis sooner rather than acquire skills. He was poor in formatting citations and managing references in APA format, had little knowledge about research design, and was reluctant to elaborate on the procedure or findings. The student had started a job in a city in Gandaki province and submitted his reports via email. He pushed hard for the thesis presentation despite my continuous efforts to make him make changes to his thesis. He ignored much feedback and still insisted to defend the research. He is yet to submit the hard copies. I have, for the final time, suggested making improvements.

Nonetheless, I do not think he has acquired the necessary skills for research. Another student has started research of similar nature but is clueless about how to move forward. I wonder what is lacking in our education that despite passing two subjects entirely dedicated to conducting research and doing many research-based assignments, they are blank about starting research.

Evaluation Lapses

Inadequate attendance is a big problem. The bigger problem is filtering based on inadequate attendance because if we bar students from the final exams, more than half students will not qualify. More attendance is related to better academic achievement (Khanal, 2019). However, no one is failing. The undocumented policy seems to provide minimum pass marks to anybody who appears for the final exam. This will degrade the quality of education in the long term. Word-by-mouth mode of communication will spread the message that without submitting assignments and making enough presence in the classes, the students can pass. So, the dean's office, which appears to be the origin of the problem, should be strict. The colleges' policy to promote quantity (for extra fees) rather than quality may also be to blame.

A coordinator in a college had told me that the 'dean's office' would return the mark sheet to the college if they would send the actual low marks (below 24) in the internal evaluation. That semester, I had endowed them the right to provide any marks. I denied providing pass marks to the students who did not complete the minimum requirements. I was not called to teach for the next batch in the same semester. I did not inquire for the reasons. I did not check the coordinator's claim about the 'dean's office' either.

Traditional Mindset

The students come with the traditional mindset that the teachers will offer them many things. They want to remain passive and listen to what teachers have to say. Very few students like to interact. Some students want to interact but they stray from the main topic and the course seems to deviate. The students need to be active and they have to work harder. They need to present. They need to discuss. The semester provides a chance for activity-based pedagogy (Mishra, 2021). The students should be activated and intrinsically motivated to learn. Self-directed learning is the key to adult learning (Gyawali et al., 2011).

In CDP in 2018, a student presented a replica of a friend's research report in Psy553. I rejected the report. Associate Professor Kabita Khati was the external examiner. We gave them a second chance to submit the work within a week but they could not and dropped out. It was the first time I met and knew the examiner. She invited me to tutor Psy553 at PKC for the following batch. At TRC in 2019, two students submitted the

same assignment via email. I rejected them and gave chance to rewrite. They did. At PKC in the same year, a student submitted the copy of friends' data for a test construction project of Psy559 and was caught after the viva voce was completed. I reported the misdeed to the coordinator. I think the colleges should clarify the rules during orientation for the first semester and take strict policy to implement the rules.

Student commitment is needed. The current curriculum in the semester system of MA demands their full-time commitment. Unfortunately, without working, the students find it very hard to live in a metropolis that is too expensive. A study (Karki, 2016) concluded that students do not take internal exams seriously. So, the qualified students need to be taken who can work committedly towards the successful completion of their degree.

Theoretical Domination

The current course was supposed to be practice-oriented (especially in the third and fourth semesters dedicated to specialization). The course of Clinical Psychology can be made really practice-oriented in two phases: psychosocial intervention in the community under the supervision of a mentor in the third semester and internship in the clinical setting in the fourth semester. In fact, the former practice should have excelled by the completion of a bachelor's degree. In that case, practice in the final two semesters can be devoted to teaching and learning the practice in the clinical setting. Similarly, the third and fourth semesters in other specializations (like Industrial and Organizational Psychology) can be designed in phases. This design is applicable if a Master's degree can be made independent (viz, less concerned with the bachelor's degree). Alternatively, the theoretical and practical works can be kept in a manner that the bachelor's degree and master's degree become two sections of a continuum.

Currently, there is a dearth of places (like clinical settings for clinical psychology) to take the students for practicum. One solution for this problem is that the university can coordinate with other governmental offices like Health Ministry to get connected to the private or public mental hospitals (or psychiatry wards/ psychological divisions). Industry-academia collaboration should be guided by policy and laws. The industry can provide the updates about changing market needs to the academia, it prepares such human resources, and industry provides the chance to students to train (or learn skills as interns), and finally hires the graduates as employees. In this way, the industry benefits because the cost/time to hunt for qualified employees is reduced. The students are benefitted as they get employment. The university is benefitted as the professors can be stronger and their knowledge factory can contribute significantly to the community and country.

Poor Quality Control (QC)

Even though the university is aware that monitoring is necessary (HERP, 2019), I did not notice that monitoring is done. I did not see a single day that anybody from Dean's Office came for monitoring or supervision. The quality is to be maintained during admission, teaching-learning, administration, and examination (including practicum and thesis). On the other hand, I did not know many instances when teachers were invited for training or discussion. Without participation, how will the university prepare future leaders?

I got some training from the university. One was about orientation about grading in the semester system. There were hundreds of participants in a single hall and the training began late. I did not find the training effective. The next training was online about the use of MS Teams. The internet quality of trainers was poor and it was also distracting. The final training was about the use of e-resources to access from TUCL. Unfortunately, the resources it offers are not enough for a world-class research culture. I felt like I need training for andragogy but I had nowhere to go. I also am seeking opportunities for Ph.D. in Psychology but am helpless. I know that there is a Coordination Division but I am not hopeful that it will bring any chances for growth. I knew only one time that it offered opportunities of Ph.D. in some other subjects. Is it not a responsibility of an organization to help an employee with career development?

An entrance exam is the best alternative to filter students who are not committed to learning. Alternatively, as in foreign universities, clear categorization of students as full-timers and part-timers and their management accordingly is an option. The lifestyle is getting more expensive year by year. So, the students engaging in jobs need to be attracted by a provision of part-time studentship.

Sticking to the evaluation standards is a great necessity. Teachers get lenient frequently. For example, the minimum requirement of 80% attendance has been repeatedly compromised owing to the emotional attachment to students and *political* threats. For the teachers to hold to the standards, their safety should be ensured. Rather than having to get personal, a set of clear and strict rules should dictate our decisions.

Suggestions to increase the effectiveness of the semester system

There are various ways to increase the effectiveness of the semester system. To achieve that end, all the parties concerned- management, administrators, colleges, teachers, and students- should be more responsible. The university has already thought of many measures to improve (HERP, 2019) but I offer some suggestions.

Hybridizing Teaching-learning

Pandemic has highlighted that online mode of educating is possible and the time is ripe. The hybrid mode (i.e., both physical and online modes combined) can be more effective when the price of petroleum has surged. Care should be taken to ensure the quality of online education. For example, urban/rural residing made a significant difference in the perception of online and distance learning (ODL) quality (Upadhayaya et al., 2021). The challenges of affordability and digital literacy (Kusum, 2019) are to be addressed properly, particularly for the students of rural origin and poor families. During the pandemic, technological, organizational, and environmental issues impeded teachers' sense of duty and their attitude to teach online (Laudari et al., 2021). These issues should be resolved sooner than later if we are to adopt the hybrid mode of educating.

Different kinds of evidence-based andragogy may also be tried. Cross-disciplinary exchange of teaching methods may be an option to diversify teaching and training methods. For example, Shankar (2009) found that role-play borrowed from behavioral science was a fun experience in learning among medical students and they learned perspectives of patients better.

I have been using diary-writing assignments for some years now. Among various psychological issues, I assign one to students so that they can know themselves better and learned it simultaneously. For example, I had let students of Psy551 write a happiness diary in January of 2022. For fifteen days, they had to write a diary in which they had to answer the questions like *what things did you expect to make you happy, what made you happy today, how you expressed happiness, and what did you intentionally do to be happy* daily. This technique can be applied later as a skill for counseling, psychotherapy, and self-reflection. It proves to be very useful andragogy. Many students have reacted to these techniques as reflexive, therapeutic, and insightful. A student reacted to the happiness diary, "... writing happiness diary was an enjoyable experience for me because it was something new that I never thought of doing." Another student wrote, "Writing diary need not necessarily keep me happy all the time, or even discipline me; nonetheless, it kept me informing about the formation of emotions and their changes on a regular basis".

Removing Teacher-Student Hierarchy

The students seem to be communicating with teachers very less on and off campus. The students might perceive themselves as lower in rank than teachers. So, they shun open communication with the teachers. Teachers also may not be accessible to the students. A reason to avoid communication with teachers is being unable to catch up. The horizontal communication between students and teachers would make learning

better. An important aspect of the semester system is that it gives enough chance for interaction (K. Dahal, 2019). So, they should interact with teachers without hesitation. Still, the student should not forget that they are students.

I have made a document mentioning the terms and conditions for the thesis supervision. It is to caution a protégé to stick to standards and ethics while conducting research. I encourage my students to communicate fearlessly. The first two points are about communication: "1. Communicate via official email or telephone conversation. Do not hesitate to write or talk to me. I welcome frank communication. You can share your background, difficulties, and facilities anytime. Please DO NOT communicate via Viber or similar other media (because I am not online all the time; it takes time to type; mostly, the network is poor because of slow internet). I cannot reply to your SMS also. 2. You may call me on workdays (10 am-5 pm). I may not receive calls when I am in the classroom (including virtual ones), vehicle, washroom, or kitchen. You can try again (and again) without hesitation." I want students to communicate freely with me.

Documentation

In a meeting about the overall experience and internal marking at CDP, one among all participants (part-time and permanent faculty) suggested having a separate practicum subject so that the repeated themes of practicums in existing subjects are managed. Another participant suggested knowing the professional and academic background of students so they can be assigned customized practicum. I highlighted the documentation of teachers' assignments. I argued that when the teacher makes the habit of keeping records of content and procedure of assignment in written form, they can discipline themselves and the students. This also serves as a part of semester/unit/lesson planning. The documentation is evidence for any possible disputes in the future. It can be the basis of performance appraisal and research also. I also added that the physical-offline hybrid model should be adopted to take classes and assign/submit the practical works. The use of Google Classroom or Assignment function in Microsoft Teams or such other technology can allow both teachers and students to have a proper record of what has been assigned, how it should be done, and what the deadline is. With the technological advances all around, the teachers want to increase their digital competencies regardless of organizational neglect and they use some of their abilities outside the classroom for teaching activities (Laudari, 2019). Mention of SPSS and NVivo application in the curriculum (CDP, 2013) is a good start but the fact that whole semester teaching is manageable using technology cannot be forgotten. The use of technology comes with various challenges. So, safe and responsible use of information and communication technology (ICT) should be a high

priority and should be incorporated in academic culture (Dhakal & Pant, 2016) from day one.

The need for Ethical Review Board to review research proposals has been long realized. If we can allow thesis students to pass their proposal through this board, the proposal will be kept in record. Moreover, the quality of research will go up. Now, the studies are being done just to fulfill the requirement. If the students start to conduct research as per needs of society, society can also be benefitted. The resources they squander now for research in vain will also get utilized as well. The teachers and professors can use this platform to get internationally published. Since this board is lacking, international journals deny publication without ethical approval. The health-related research proposals can be applied to Nepal Health Research Council (NHRC) but Psychology is not about mental health only. So, there are difficulties. I had to dillydally some offers of international collaborative research because TU had not got such a board.

Connecting Curriculum with the Context

The imported content cannot address the needs of society. Even though the teaching-learning has transitioned to the semester system, a significant contribution cannot be expected if the native knowledge and beliefs are ignored. The university should provide an environment conducive to adjusting native knowledge. The curricular practices need reform (Rai & Gaire, 2021) in the state where classroom lectures do not address local professional practices (Kurata et al., 2020). Contextual education is necessary (Lamsal, 2021). The courses in university should be guided by the needs of society most of the time. The curricula should address those needs.

Increasing Educator-Management Coordination

I have realized that the teachers have the joy of learning while teaching but the joy fades as the teachers feel that there is no destination of that learning journey. I was willing to take new subjects to teach initially as I believed that I could expand my knowledge horizon but am no longer excited to take on a new subjects. The solution can be associating the learning process with the performance appraisal process. If learning, publication, and promotion can be linked, the teachers will keep getting motivated to learn and teach forever. Now, seniority is the biggest determinant for promotion. The number of research, citations and publications should be the basis for growth.

Sometimes, teachers are over-working and investing a lot for the students but the indifference of managers (or coordinators or administrators) creates a difficulty in delivering. For example, the laptops are not repaired on time after they get defunct; the projectors for presentations are not set up before the class time. They may be

indifferent to students' process of skills development (B. Joshi, 2021). The results are not announced timely (Subedi, 2019). The management should be ready to change ways of doing things as the times or circumstances change. For example, it should have been prompt in taking online exams during the pandemic of COVID-19 as other universities in Nepal like Nepal Open University itself did (Khadka & Poudel, 2020, p. 73).

By the year 2022, the internet has become essential for academic purposes. In my department at TRC lying in the Ghantaghar building, I do not have my computer and internet facilities. I can use my laptop computer but I cannot fetch the internet devices everywhere. Even though the classes are physical, sharing resources is done online. Sometimes, references are to be looked up instantly/urgently. Sometimes, the use of some applications has to be shown online. For example, I could demonstrate how to use Google Classroom or access TUCL resources online if there were internet. The management has long ignored this need for the internet and teaching efficacy has to suffer.

During my visit to PKC, I saw that there were interns doing administrative tasks. The department of psychology was looking for a part-time employee which was not availed for some reasons but they decided to keep interns. "The interns hired for six months are more motivated to work than permanent employees", said the campus chief of TRC in a meeting to discuss hiring a lab assistant for Bachelor's degree. Creative ways of management can be practiced in a situation when human resources are lacking.

Involving interns to fulfill the scarcity of human resources is a good option. The young persons needing experience for job will also be benefitted by being exposed to some technical and some management things during the internship. For example, if the professor is very busy, the interns (lab/teaching assistants) can aid him to supervise students in the lab, with psychological tests, for thesis/research, or during field trips.

Investing in Human Capital

There is no doubt that the teachers need training (Lamsal, 2021) to make the semester system more effective. So do administrative employees. As described above, the teachers cannot give outcomes if they do not have proper seating arrangements or are deprived of contemporary technologies. The university has to actively help its professors in career development.

The other things can also be improved. Addressing the zeitgeist like designing a gender-responsive curriculum is also needed (Dhungana et al., 2021). Currently, some illustrations, not curriculum content, may be promoting gender bias (Gurung & Rajbanshi, 2020). Other issues may be sustainable development, integration of

technology in assignments, and taking cases of recent events covered in mass media. As highlighted earlier, continuous revision of the curriculum is necessary. The new teachers should be socialized in the organization's culture/climate, available resources, and how they can take help from available employees. Additionally, antidotes for the flaws presented above should be found. I have suggested some already while discussing the problems.

Discussion

In a nutshell, the semester system would be better than the yearly system (N. P. Sharma, 2016) but we have not been able to realize its effectiveness optimally because of practical reasons and our background of financial weakness. The structural synchronization with international universities is a good thing but are our students learning desired skills and knowledge? This question does not have a positive answer yet. Even though the university is set to increase its capacity in terms of animate and inanimate resources (HERP, 2019) in the future, it seems capacity-strengthening should be done urgently. The attitude for continuous improvement is necessary. Institute of Engineering is trying to improve its examination process (Bajracharya et al., 2018). This approach to improvement can be adopted by other institutions and faculties also. Furthermore, how to make tertiary education successful can be modeled from the higher education in developed nation (B. B. Acharya, 2019). Market-driven education and curriculum change/update is necessary.

Yearly to semester transition has offered some merits and some challenges. In the semester system, the students are more active and more in touch with teachers. So, their chance of being better groomed has increased, the major challenge with the semester system is the lack of resources. More teachers are needed, and the teachers need to work more. The current compensation strategy of the university makes it impossible to attract the teachers to university to offer them professorship as a long-term career. Except for permanent faculty, all the part-time teachers use university as a platform to jump into another career, country, or occupation. Had there been more employment opportunities in the country, the current workload and salary imbalance would not hold the permanent faculties in the colleges either. Because the payment is so low, the teachers work in many colleges and cannot dedicate enough time to maintain quality.

The semester system would be effective if students were full-timers, teachers were professional, curricula were application-oriented and innovative, teaching methods were scientific, the library was resourceful, the academic calendar was followed well, and there was a good academic environment (Baral et al., 2019). The teachers seem to have a positive attitude toward the semester system (Bista, 2016) but the students seem not to have felt differences between the annual and semester systems (Pandit,

2016). Learning by doing is the inherent philosophy of the semester system (Dahal, 2021) but the psychology department may not have been able to adopt it fully in practice.

Epilogue

I hope things will get better down the track. In almost five years of my tenure, I have gotten fed up with the ongoing subpar practices, unhelpful behaviors from management, and students coming without interest. Still, a factor to console is the fact that we all are learning and growing from our mistakes. The Vision 2030 of TU (HERP, 2019) is promising and I expect the university will implement its plans sooner than later. I also believe that colleges' administration will improve to add quality to the semester system and the entire educating process. I also expect that circumstances will hold me in my job at TU and not obligate me to switch it in search of a better alternative.

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